

Comparison of 3D and GIS approach for estimation rooftop solar potential in urban areas

Author Name^{1*}, Author Name² and Author Name^{1,2} – do NOT fill for now!

¹ Department, Institution, City, Country – do NOT fill for now!

² Department, Institution, City, Country – do NOT fill for now!

*E-mail: name@institution.edu – do NOT fill for now!

Abstract. Estimating rooftop solar power potential and PV power potential is in last two decades one of the most important topics in the field of decarbonisation and sustainable energy. In terms of calculation tools, 3D softwares are usually more computationally and manually demanding compared to GIS tools, especially in the scale of urban blocks, districts or entire cities. On the other hand, lower demands of GIS tools go hand in hand with possibly lower accuracy. Therefore, it can be beneficial to calibrate the GIS model using real measured data or trusted results of 3D software and then use it for the calculation of larger urban areas. In this paper the GIS software was calibrated using long-term meteorological data and PVGIS data on horizontal plane. Next it was compared with PVGIS and 3D model on a single tilted plane, with a fair agreement. Finally, the GIS and 3D software were compared using sums of total annual incident solar energy on five selected roof segments within real urban area in the city centre of Prague. Despite several issues to be solved the difference in the total solar energy received by five roofs was at maximum $\pm 14\%$.

1. Introduction

The solar potential is a fundamental parameter in the field of PV power estimations. One of the most promising surfaces to be used for PV installation are building rooftops [1]. Together with installations of floating PV on larger water bodies (reservoirs) and along roads and trails, these together are by JRC referred as R3 installations and present a viable option for installation of PV panels without occupying additional land [1]. Currently, also PV installations in agriculture dwellings (i.e. agrivoltaics) seem very promising [2].

In last two decades has been made a huge progress in the field of estimating rooftop solar energy potential in urban areas as well as progress in new calculation tools [3-5]. This was forced by the increasing need of using renewable energy sources [6]. Recently, for estimation of solar potential of large areas the most advantageous seems to be GIS tools, often combined with artificial intelligence and deep-learning approaches for generation 3D model of studied area [7]. Still the most accurate seem to be using a 3D software tools such as Rhino3D [8]. These are however manually and computationally highly demanding. Therefore, a natural way to calculate solar potential in larger urban areas is to calibrate the GIS model based on more accurate data, measured data or outputs from 3D software, and use the GIS tool for larger areas such as building blocks, city districts or entire cities. This paper presents a process of calibrating GIS model based on local meteorological data and results of accurate 3D software in terms of estimating rooftop

solar potential in urban areas. At first were compared data of annual global total insolation on horizontal plane (Gth [kWh/m²/a]) and global diffuse insolation on horizontal plane (Gdh [kWh/m²/a]) with long-term data from local meteorological station and PVGIS tool [9]. In the next step were compared insolation data on sloped unshaded surface and finally were compared total annual incident solar energy on five roofs within an urban block located in the centre of the city of Prague, including shading by real surrounding environment.

2. Methods

2.1 Software and input data

In this study were used two software tools. The 3D simulations were conducted in the Rhino3D 6.0[8] with Ladybug plugins. The base 3D model was free-downloaded from website of Prague Institute of Planning and Development (IPR) [10]. In order to maximize the accuracy of calculations the annual irradiance component has been used, translating the geometry and relevant information into a Radiance tool [11] for raytracing analysis using an enhanced 2phase method, which accurately models direct sun by tracing rays from each sensor to the solar position at each hour of the calculation. The input weather file contains hourly data of typical meteorological year TMYx epw file for the set of years 2007-2021. The solar radiation used in the TMYx file originated from the ERA5 [12] reanalysis dataset provided by Oikolab.

For the GIS calculations was used ArcGIS pro 3.4 [13] and solar radiation tool “Area Solar Radiation”. The base digital elevation model (DEM) and polygons of building footprints were downloaded from the same institute as data for the 3D model, the IPR [10]. The DEM has a resolution (the cell size) of 1x1 m². The solar radiation tool in ArcGIS pro uses spatial solar model for the simulation of the sun orbit around the Earth. Therefore, no input meteorological data are needed for irradiation calculations. There are only two parameters to be adjusted to represent the local atmospheric conditions, the atmospheric transmissivity (T) and the diffuse proportion (DP). Although the default values of the parameters are meant for a good approximation of real annual insolation it was shown that calibration of these parameters for local conditions is very beneficial [14,15].

2.2 Location and reference solar data

The location to be studied is the city centre of Prague (Czech Republic), 14.42°E, 50.08°N. As a reference solar data were used 16-year (hourly) data from local meteorological station. By simply averaging the data was established a reference irradiation year for purposes of this study. Figure 1 shows the reference year using monthly insolation values on horizontal plane, the total (Gth) and diffuse (Gdh) part. The right axis shows ratio of the diffusive and total insolation (Gdh/Gth).

Although for the calculation in Rhino software were used different meteorological data (see Section 2.1), they are not far from the reference year, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Long-term average of meteorological solar data (reference year) and meteorological data as input in Rhino3D (based on ERA5) [12].

3 Calculations

3.1 Calculations on horizontal plane

As a base line for further complex scenarios the 3D model and the GIS model was used to calculate insolation on an unshaded horizontal plane. The annual total (Hth) and diffuse (Hdh) horizontal insolation values were compared. For more complex comparison, also data from PVGIS tool [9] were compared, see Table 1.

Except for the ArcGIS Pro having default parameters, all sources are in good agreement with the reference meteorological year. In terms of (Hth), the maximum difference is ca. $\pm 4\%$ and in terms of diffuse horizontal insolation (Hdh) up to $\pm 17\%$. The ArcGIS having default parameters differs from the reference year by -20% (see Table 1). The parameters were then manually adjusted for getting values similar to Rhino software because these two softwares will be used in further steps of the solar radiation analysis. Best fitting parameters were set to $T = 0.44$ and $DP = 0.59$.

Table 1. Comparison of annual solar radiation data on horizontal plane.

Source	data information	Hth		Hdh		Hdh/Hth (-)
		(kWh/m ²)	dif.	(kWh/m ²)	dif.	
Prague meteostation (CHI) (reference year)	average (2004-2019)	1173	0%	585	0%	0.50
Rhino3D 6.0	TMYx ERA5	1224	4%	659	13%	0.54
PVGIS ver.5.3	PVGIS-ERA5 (2005-2023)	1138	-3%	487	-17%	0.43
PVGIS ver.5.3	PVGIS-SARAH3 (2005-2023)	1171	0%	569	-3%	0.49
ArcGIS Pro 3.1	AreaSolarRadiation tool (uniform overcast sky; default T=0.5, DH=0.3)	942	-20%			
ArcGIS Pro 3.1	AreaSolarRadiation tool (uniform overcast sky;	1220	4%	650	11%	0.53

3.2 Calculations on tilted plane

Effect of tilted plane was briefly studied on a single unshaded surface, similarly to the previous comparison on the horizontal plane. A slope of 38° and azimuth 165° clockwise from north was selected for this purpose. This time only results of Rhino, ArcGIS and PVGIS were compared, see Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of annual solar radiation data on tilted plane.

Source	data information	Hth (kWh/m ²)	dif.
Rhino3D 6.0	TMYx ERA5	1398	0%
PVGIS ver.5.3	PVGIS-ERA5 (2005-2023)	1411	1%
PVGIS ver.5.3	PVGIS-SARAH3 (2005-2023)	1365	-2%
ArcGIS Pro 3.1	AreaSolarRadiation tool (uniform overcast sky; default T=0.44, DH=0.59)	1325	-5%

3.3 Calculations on real roof segments

Five roof segments within a block of buildings in the centre of the city of Prague were selected for the final analysis. Roofs were selected to fulfil different parameters that can play a role in the total annual incident solar energy, see Figure 2. Roofs have different orientation, and some are shaded or structured.

Figure 2. Orthophoto view on urban block in the city centre of Prague with highlighted roof segments to be analysed.

Figure 3. Comparison of orthophoto view (left), Rhino3D model view (middle) and ArcGIS Pro view (right) on a single roof segment.

One of the main problems can be towards the resolution of the GIS model, which is 1x1 m and small structures in the plane of the roof will not be respected, but they affect the azimuth and slope of particular calculation cell. The more complex the roof would be, the higher this potential error. In Figure 3 can be seen difference between the orthophoto view at roof 1, the same image in the 3D software and in the GIS software.

In the 3D software is every segment of the roof defined in terms of its shape, area, azimuth and slope. In contrast, in the GIS software the roof is defined by the top-view polygon and raster of cells with an elevation information that define orientation and slope of the roof. Since most tested roof segments are tilted, their top-view polygons do not represent their real area. If the roof slope is around 30°, the area of the roof is ca. 15 % larger than the polygon. On the other hand, the result of used solar radiation tool is the annual insolation (kWh/m²/a) in the location of each calculation cell. Although the cells have top-view dimensions 1x1 m² these insolation values do not correspond to the cell area, only to its location, orientation and slope. To obtain real incident solar energy on the sloped roof represented by 1x1 m cell, the insolation value has to be multiplied by the real roof area within this cell. For this purpose, was calculated slope of each cell and real area of roof in the cell. This raster was then multiplied by the insolation raster to get real insolation in the whole top-view roof polygon.

The described operation had however another limitation. Due to the raster resolution, the automatically calculated slopes at the edges of roofs near eaves and on the border with another roof segments often present slopes higher than 80°. These represent a vertical surface (wall) in the geometry that is due to low resolution not 90° and the model includes the surface into the rooftop calculation. Problem is that calculated “real” area of these cells can be up to 10 m² (see Fig. 4) and at the same time the cell can have quite high insolation value calculated based on different GIS tool. By multiplying the two values can be reached unrealistically high insolation values in the cell, see Figure 4. To avoid this, all slopes higher than 60° were set to maintain 60° which means, that such erroneous cell represents a roof area of 2 m². Although this phenomenon can be studied in greater detail, the solution was assumed to be enough for this study and eliminating majority of the erroneous cells.

Figure 4. Approach to avoid cells with unrealistic solar energy values: a) initial calculation of solar energy, b) raster of real cell areas affected by side walls, c) raster of (a) and (b) multiplied containing error cells, d) adjusted “area” raster without affection of side walls, e) raster of solar energy on “real” roof area (multiplication of (a) and (d)).

In Table 3 can be seen results of total incident solar energy on all roof segments calculated in Rhino and ArcGIS Pro software. Despite very different calculation approaches the resulting values are in good agreement. It can be seen that mean insolation on selected roof segments differs up to $\pm 8\%$, the roof area up to $\pm 11\%$ and the total annual incident solar energy up to $\pm 14\%$.

Table 3. Comparison of calculated annual solar energy and area of five roof segments in the city of Prague based on Rhino3D and ArcGIS approaches.

		insolation (kWh/m ² /a)	area (m ²)	total incident solar energy (MWh/a)
roof 1	Rhino3D	1156.8	152.0	175.8
	ArcGIS Pro	1150.1	142.6	164.0
	dif.	-0.6%	-6.2%	-6.7%
roof 2	Rhino3D	992.0	180.8	179.4
	ArcGIS Pro	915.6	200.3	183.4
	dif.	-7.7%	10.8%	2.3%
roof 3	Rhino3D	321.8	189.4	61.0
	ArcGIS Pro	325.1	177.5	57.7
	dif.	1.0%	-6.3%	-5.3%
roof 4	Rhino3D	847.8	82.1	69.6
	ArcGIS Pro	798.4	90.3	72.1
	dif.	-5.8%	9.9%	3.5%
roof 5	Rhino3D	830.0	186.1	154.5
	ArcGIS Pro	806.9	165.2	133.3
	dif.	-2.8%	-11.2%	-13.7%
total			790.5	640.3
			775.9	610.5
			-1.9%	-4.7%

4 Discussion

The parameters of ArcGIS solar radiation tool were at first manually adjusted to fit the total and diffuse insolation on horizontal plane with the meteorological data used in Rhino (see Figure4). Table 3 shows that after this adjustment, the annual incident solar energy on selected roof segments in the city centre of Prague corresponds well with a reference values calculated in Rhino software. None of the five selected roofs with different shading, slopes and orientation differ more than $\pm 14\%$ from the reference values. Moreover, these results contain some amount of error given by the calculation of the real area of roof segments in the GIS software. At the same time the differences in solar radiation data mostly correspond to differences in roof area, see Table 3. It can be therefore estimated that if the area in both models (3D and GIS) would be the same, the differences in incident solar energy will be even lower.

In the context of all five roof segments together which can represent a building block made out of these roofs, the difference between models is only -4.7% , which can be considered a very good agreement. On the other hand, a set of five roofs is still not statistically sufficient to draw any major conclusions about the accuracy of the GIS software. The preliminary results are, however, promising.

Based on current results a further work can be proposed: 1) performing a comparison of the full building block containing ca. 30-40 buildings for a few different types of urban areas (e.g. city centre with historical buildings, suburban area, building stocks and industrial areas), 2) The calculation can be performed not only using the annual totals, but also using monthly values with a calibration of GIS parameters in each month, 3) the comparison of incident rooftop solar energy can be performed using total values of incident solar energy as well as only the diffusive part.

5 Conclusion

Based on step-by step comparison of 3D and GIS approach for estimation annual incident solar energy on selected roof segments seems that using the GIS software can be accurate enough for usual purposes. However, this can be done only by proper calibration of the calculation parameters and careful postprocessing, especially towards calculating real roof area. The comparison of five selected roof segments within real urban area showed maximum $\pm 14\%$ difference in annual incident solar energy compared to a reference 3D software.

This study was limited only to solar potential of rooftops in general, without more practical insight, such as that considerable area of selected rooftops is covered with windows, ventilation exhausts and chimneys. Therefore, for further use of the data in terms of estimating realistic PV power potential is needed additional practical analysis.

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